

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19280406

Gender Effect Of Project-Based Teaching Method In Developing Students' Technical Skill In Electrical Installation And Maintenance Work In Technical Colleges For Sustainable Knowledge Based Economy.

¹Obi, Catherine Odinaka Chinyere Ph.D; ²Akamobi, Ogochukwu Grace Ph.D; ³Okoye Enemuo Dominic .C. & ⁴Okereke Chibuike Ifeanyi

**Department Of Electrical/Electronics Technology Education,
Federal College Of Education (Technical), Umunze Anambra State**

¹obikate4@gmail.com 07057466640

²ogochukwuakamobi@gmail.com 07082182921

³minicjay@yahoo.com 07037735237

⁴datcorrectguy10@gmail.com 08061595299

ABSTRACT

The study focused on gender differential of Project-Based Teaching Method on Technical Skill Development of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A quasi-experimental design involving experimental and control group plus pre-test and post-test was adopted. Population of the study consists of all the 390 National Technical Certificate (NTC) year II Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (EIMW) Students in Technical Colleges. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 80 students from two schools based on the number of students and availability of facilities. Instrument used for the study was Technical Skill Performance Test in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (TSPTEIMW) which contains 3 practical/activity based questions in relation with the Technical College EIMW Curriculum for National Technical Certificate (NTC) II. The instrument was validated by three experts two from Department of Electrical/Electronics Federal College of Education (Technical), Umunze and one from measurement and evaluation, Federal College of education (Technical), Umunze. The reliability was determined by administering TSPTEIMW on a trial group of an intact class of 30 students which was not included in the study. Reliability co-efficient of the scores was established using Cronbach Alpha formula which yielded 0.82. Data collected from the study were analyzed using arithmetic mean to answer the research questions While Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study indicated that there was significant effect of the treatment (project-based teaching method) on EIMW student's technical skill development. The effect of gender on technical skill development in EIMW was found insignificant. However, a significant interaction effect was observed between gender and teaching method. Based on the findings, it was recommended that EIMW teachers should pay attention to the issue of gender differences in their instructional delivery. Also educational implications of the study were raised.

Keywords: technical skill, development, gender, students

INTRODUCTION

Technical education at all levels of education system emphasizes acquisition of practical skill and knowledge relating to occupation in various sectors of the economy and social life (Okoye 2016). In furtherance, curriculum planners have continued to enrich and expand the curriculum with contents to enable students meet the demands of occupational changes occasioned by technological advancement. It has been found that as new contents are being introduced into the curriculum, principles and practices has to change to be able to face the challenges in the world of work. The constant review and overloading of curriculum has created implementation problems for classroom teachers. It is common knowledge that some instructors may be limiting the classroom instructions to mere transmission of facts. In the view of Ombugus and Umaru (2016), monitoring of the instructors in teaching skill based courses (electrical installation maintenance work inclusive) to meet technological advancement is crucial. Learners' development should be the focal point. Additionally, the authors further stated that technical skill development is aimed at ensuring self-reliance for the end products and thus practice must be emphasized over theory. Furthermore, skill development process (instruction) should focus on knowledge gained after instruction delivery and the practice of the technical skill learnt. Therefore, since technical skills are usually aimed at practical purposes the process should be learner centered. When teachers employ appropriate teaching methods as contained in the curriculum that matches technical education programme objectives (Okoye, 2016) skill development process will be easier.

Over the years, the conventional method of instructional delivery has been dominantly used in Nigerian schools. This method of teaching according to Aguba (2015) is simply an act of spoon feeding learners with information or facts which has done more harm than good for courses that are skill based. Akem in Ayonmike (2014) stated that conventional method is good for large classes since much work could be easily covered in a short time but it makes the teacher a custodian of information, ideas, and knowledge, thereby denying learners the opportunity to develop technical skills which is needed for nation building. The resultant effect is the low achievements as evidenced in students learning outcomes portrayed both in the results of internal and external examinations. This could be the reason, Olokede and Olusanjo (2009) submitted that many researchers have adduced that low achievement in technical college public examinations is traceable to teaching methods employed by technical teachers. Furthermore, Edu, Ayang, and Idaka (2012) posited that conventional (lecture and demonstration) method cannot improve technical skill development of students in technical college trades.

In technical colleges, electrical installation and maintenance work is a trade in Electrical/Electronic option and provides learners with practical skills and knowledge required for functional electrical/electronic technicians. Such persons are needed for employment in organizations like Electricity Distribution Company (EDC), manufacturing, mining, oil and gas industries. Electrical installation and maintenance work comprises three modules namely; Domestic and Industrial Installation, Cable Jointing and Battery Charging and Winding of electrical machine, (NABTEB 2010). Additionally, graduates of this programme are expected to develop technical skills in installing, operating, maintaining and repairing of electrically energized systems such as residential, commercial and industrial building. Electrical installation and maintenance work ought to be taught effectively.

Supporting this view, Yinusa (2014) lamented that in spite of all the important roles science and technology play in the development of the nations, their enhancement in Nigeria has been low. In the same vein Eze and Osuyi (2018) affirmed that even though the indispensability of technical education in the production of skilled trade persons for nation building and development of society has been universally acknowledged, the outcome of the implementation of technical education programme in Nigeria is still not encouraging. This is why many researchers, technical educators and other stakeholders have been searching for more effective ways to ensure effective teaching and learning of technical skills in technical education programmes for the benefit of the students and the nation.

A good number of researchers;(Omeje, 2011; Edu, Ayang, Idaka, 2012; Ayonmike, 2014; and Amaechi, Thoman, (2016) recommended that project-based teaching methods could be effective methods for

teaching technical skill in technical education programmes because they encourage active participation of students in the teaching and learning process and as well enhance their technical skill development. This could be applicable to technical skill in electrical installation and maintenance work because when students understand the principles of a subject, they can construct knowledge of the subject, retain the knowledge and apply it practically in given situations. In support of this view, Abdulrahman (2012) averred that skills for practical knowledge are best learnt through giving students' assignments/projects and practice.

Project-based method of teaching is one of the instructional methods used by technical instructors as it enhances students' participation. According to Omeje and Onaga (2015), project-based teaching method involves units of activities carried out by the students in a spirit of purpose to accomplish a defined, attractive and seemingly attained predetermined goals based on their background knowledge and experience. This will enable students to conceptualize the content and put the task into practice repeatedly in order to improve their technical skill development. It is, therefore, very essential according to the authors that the method teachers use in teaching skill courses should stimulate and sustain the interest of all students irrespective of gender.

Agbejaye and Adegbola (2017) affirmed that gender could have influence on students' achievement and interest in different fields of study. The authors further asserted that professions like engineering, arts and crafts are generally regarded as men's field while others like catering, typing and nursing are regarded as women's. It is common knowledge, tasks that are complex and difficult are allocated to boys whereas girls are expected to handle the relatively easy and less demanding tasks. As a result of this way of thinking, the society tends to regard females as the weaker "Sex" and the average Nigeria girl goes to school with these fixed stereotypes. Addey, Robertson and Venville (2002) and Udouo (2005) reported that there is no significant difference between boys and girls in their cognitive acceleration. This view also agrees with Obi (2021) who reported a significant difference in the mean performance test score of boys and girls in favour of the boys. Also, some literature evidence is questioning the validity of sex difference performance, since this depends among other things on students' level of intelligence and interest on subject (Eze, Ezenwafor & Obi 2015). Therefore, there is need to investigate gender effect of project-based teaching method in developing students' technical skill in electrical installation and maintenance work in Technical Colleges in Anambra State for sustainable knowledge based economy.

Statement of the Problem

Skill development in different trades is critical for sustainable knowledge based economy. Technical skills in the study of electrical installation and maintenance work among students in Technical Colleges have been dwindling over the years. Hassan and Babawuro (2013) reported that most of the products of vocational and technical education programmes in tertiary institutions in Nigeria are half-baked as they lack technical skills and therefore are unable to function effectively in the world of work on graduation. This is why they are unable to exhibit the technical skills required to become self-dependent especially as they lack clear understanding of the theories and principles of electrical installation and maintenance work. This ugly trend could be attributed mainly to instructional methods used by teachers since the use of instructional methods that match the objectives of the programme will increase students' interest in the study as well as equip and empower them with skills to fit into jobs in the society. More also, Technical education curriculum content creates varying learning process difficulties for students on account of their inherent individual differences according to Duze (2011) are sometimes the result of poor methods of acquiring and processing technical information of which the students may be unaware.

The problem of this study is that performance in theory and principles of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students especially the female among them in Technical Colleges in Technical Skill Test in NABTEB Examinations has consistently been poor in recent times. Although such other factors like parental and societal influence can be implicated for the ugly trend, instructional methods used by teachers could be a key factor (Eze and Osuyi, 2018). The popular use of conventional (chalk-talk) instructional methods by teachers in technical colleges may have be unsuitable for technical skills development especially in male dominated discipline. Project-based teaching method may likely have

varying effects on gender. It is imperative for this study to answer the question “what are the effects of project-based teaching method on the technical skill development of male and female students in electrical installation and maintenance work in Technical Colleges?”

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine:

1. What differences exist in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught in electrical installation and maintenance work using project-based teaching method and those taught using conventional teaching methods.
2. Is there any relationship between gender and teaching methods on students’ mean performance scores in Technical Skill Performance Test in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (TSPTEIMW).

Significance of the Study

The finding of this study on gender differential effect of project-based teaching method on technical skill development of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students in Technical Colleges in Anambra State would be of immense benefit to students as it would solve the problem of abstractness of technical subject by concretization of learning process. It is also hoped that the study will provide teachers, researchers, curriculum planners with relevant data needed for scientific advancement, efficiency and productivity of technical teachers in teaching process.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What difference exists between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught in electrical installation and maintenance work using project-based teaching method and those taught using conventional teaching methods?
2. What is the relationship between gender and teaching methods on students’ mean performance scores in Technical Skill Performance Test in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (TSPTEIMW)?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught in electrical installation and maintenance work using project-based teaching method and those taught using conventional teaching methods.
2. Gender and teaching methods do not have significant interaction effect on students mean performance score in Technical Skill Performance Test in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (TSPTEIMW).

METHOD

The research was carried out using Quasi-Experimental Design involving two groups. (experimental group and control group) additionally, with pre-test and post-test. The experimental group (E) was taught with project-based teaching method while the control group (C) was taught with the conventional teaching method. Pre-test was carried out on the two groups before the experiment and post-test was administered after the experiment on the two groups. This is in line with the recommendation of Uzoagulu (2011) that when subjects are pre-tested, the design is no longer true experiment but a quasi-experimental.

The study was carried out in Anambra State. The Technical Colleges in this State offer electrical installation and maintenance at National Business and Technical Board (NABTEB) Examinations. A purposive sampling technique was used to select two schools (Government Technical College Umunze and Government Technical College Utuh) based on the number of electrical installation and maintenance work students (male and female) and available facilities for teaching. Students from the two schools were grouped into two intact class of 80 students (50 males and 30 females) each. The two intact classes, one

was randomly assigned to the experimental group (GTC Umunze) with 28 males and 14 females while the remaining intact class was assigned to the control group (GTC Utuh) with 22 males and 16 females.

The instrument for data collection was the Technical Skill Performance Test in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (TSPTEIMW). This consists of three practical/activity questions based on technical college EIMW curriculum for National Technical Certificate (NTC) II students. Each question requires each student to use 1mm² twin P.V. C cable, a joint box and wiring board to make installation and also design and produce an electrical installation plan. Each question has Technical Skill Development Test Marking Guide with task description which students are expected to demonstrate to achieve: Excellent (expert) 4 points, Good (proficient) 3 points, Fair (competent) 2 points, Poor (beginner) 1 point in every step taken to accomplish the given task. The practical test covers domestic installation unit.

The Technical Skill Performance Test in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (TSPTEIMW) was validated by three experts, two from Department of Electrical/Electronics Federal College of Education (Technical), Umunze and one from Measurement and Evaluation Federal College of Education (Technical), Umunze. The validators checked the appropriateness of the practical test before use.

The reliability of the instrument was determined by administering Technical Skill Performance Test in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (TSPTEIMW) on a trial group of an intact class of 30 NTC II electrical installation and maintenance work students of Okporo Technical College, Orlu, Imo State who were not part of the population of the study. Reliability co-efficient of the scores was established using Cronbach Alpha formula which yielded 0.82.

Technical Skill Performance Test in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (TSPTEIMW) were administered to the NTC II students involved in the study by the trade teachers. 1mm² twin P.V. C cable, joint boxes and wiring boards were provided for the practical tests. The students obtained their scores on the spot from the trade teachers using the Technical Skill Development Test Marking Guide with task description. The pre- test was administered to both groups at the same time, reshuffled and administered for post-testing after one week of the treatment. Data collected from the two tests (pre and post) were used for data analysis.

The pre-test and post-test of the groups were collected and used for the analysis. Arithmetic mean and standard deviation was used for answering question one while correlations and t-test was used in analyzing research question two. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. For testing the null hypotheses, where the F-calculated was equal or greater than the F-table value at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypotheses was rejected but where the F-calculated was less than F-table value, the null hypotheses was accepted.

RESULT

Answer to Research question 1

Research question 1: *What differences exist in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught electrical installation and maintenance work using project-based teaching method and those taught using conventional teaching methods?*

Analysis of data in respect of research question one is presented in Table 1

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of experimental and control groups' performance in pre-test and post-test.

Teaching Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental Group (project-based)						
Male	22	7.27	2.18	17.68	2.74	10.41
Female	16	8.38	2.22	16.61	2.37	8.23
Control Group (conventional)						
Male	28	6.60	2.72	12.90	3.85	6.30
Female	14	7.70	1.78	11.90	2.22	4.20

Table 1 shows the pre-test and post-test performance mean scores of technical skills of male and female students taught electrical installation and maintenance work using project-based teaching method and

those taught using conventional teaching method were 7.27 and 17.68 with mean gain of 10.41 and 8.38, 16.61 with mean gain of 8.23 respectively. Those taught with conventional teaching method had 6.60 and 12.90 with mean gain of 6.30 and 7.70, 11.90 with mean gain of 4.20 respectively. However, for each of the groups, the post-test means were greater than the pre-test means with the male and female in the project-based group having a higher mean gain. This shows that project-based teaching method has more relative effect on male and female students' technical skill development in electrical installation and maintenance work than conventional teaching method.

Research question 2

1. *What is the relationship between gender and teaching methods on students' mean performance scores in Technical Skill Performance Test in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work?*

Analysis of data in respect of research question two is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Correlations and t-test of the experimental and control groups' performance in pre-test and post-test based on gender.

Group	Correlation	Sig.	t-test	Sig.
Experimental Group				
Project-based				
Male(pre&post)	0.418	0.004	-22.142	0.000
Female(pre&post)	0.000	1.000	-8.402	0.000
Control Group				
Male(pre&post)	0.568	0.000	-17.764	0.000
Female(pre&post)	0.612	0.015	-8.110	0.000

Data in table 2 show the correlation between the male and female students that were taught using project-based teaching method for pre-test and post-test is 0.418 and it is significant with a value 0.004. This shows a weak positive relationship. This means that the students' simultaneously improved their performance in both pre-test and post-test in project-based method. However, their t-test is highly significant with a value of -22.142 which means that there are significant differences in their mean scores confirming significance in the improvement of students mean score due to the intervention of the experimental process (project-based teaching method).

The correlation between female students that were taught using project-based teaching method for both pre-test and post-test was 0.000 and it is non-significant with a value of 1.000. This shows that there is no correlation between female students that were taught using project-based teaching method for pre-test and post-test. However, their t-test is highly significant with a value of -8.402 which means that there are significant differences in their mean rating scores confirming the scores of 8.38 for pre-test and 16.61 for post-test as seen in Table 1.

Similarly, the correlation between the male students that was taught using conventional method for both pre-test and post is 0.568 and it is significant with a value of 0.000. this shows a positive relationship. This implies that the students performed in the same direction in both the pre-test and post-test scores. Their t-test is also significant which means that there are significant differences in their mean scores as seen in table 1.

Similarly, the same result was obtained for their female counterparts. The correlation is 0.612 with a significant value of 0.015. Their t-test of -8.110 is also very significant showing that there are mean differences in both the pre-test and post-test scores as seen in Table 1

Hypothesis 1

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught electrical installation and maintenance work using project-based teaching method and those taught using conventional teaching methods.

Table 3: ANCOVA Table for teaching methods and gender for post-test.

Source of Variation	Sum Squares	of D.F	Mean Square	F-cal	F-tab	Sig.	Remarks
Gender	6.05	1	6.05	0.75	3.92	0.386	not rejected
Teaching	1622.4	1	1622.4	201.997		0.000	
Error	1903.6	238	8.032				
Total	26386	240					

Data in Table 3 show that the F-calculated for the 1 degree of freedom for the numerator and 238 for the denominator at 5% level of significant is 3.92 which is less than 0.75 and the p-value is 0.386 which is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis of no gender differences is hereby, not rejected. Conversely, the F-calculated for the teaching method is 201.997 which is greater than 3.92 and the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$, the null hypothesis of no differences in the mean scores for the teaching method is therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 2

Gender and teaching methods do not have significant interaction effect on students mean performance score in Technical Skill Performance Test in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work.

Table 4: ANCOVA Table for interaction effects of students' gender and teaching methods

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	D.F	Mean Square	F-cal	F-tab	Sig.	Rmks
Gender	6.05	1	6.05	0.75	3.92	0.387	Not rejected
Teaching	1201.3		1201.3	146.947	0.000		Rejected
Gender/teaching	0.200	1	0.200	0.025	0.875		Not rejected
Error	1909.6	237	8.023				
Total	2638	240					

Table 4 shows the F-calculated for the 1 degree of freedom for the numerator and 237 for the denominator at 5% level of significant is 3.92 which is less than 0.75 and the p-value is 0.387 which is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis of no gender is hereby not rejected. Conversely, the F-calculated for the teaching method is 1201.3 which is greater than 3.92 and p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$, the null hypothesis is of no significant differences in the mean scores for the teaching method is therefore, rejected. The F-calculated for the gender and teaching methods is 0.200. The F-tabulated with 1 numerator degree of freedom and 236 denominator degree of freedom is 3.92 and the p-value is 0.875. Since $0.025 < 3.92$ and $0.875 > 0.05$, there are no interaction effect between the gender and teaching methods.

DISCUSSION

Data presented in table 1 indicated that male and female taught using project-based teaching method has higher mean difference scores of 10.41 and 8.23 while the male and female students taught with conventional teaching method have the lowest mean difference scores of 6.30 and 4.20 respectively. It is clear from the result that the project-based teaching method is more effective than the conventional teaching method Omeje (2011).

Results in table 2 shows that the correlation for male between pre-test and post-test for project-based teaching method has a positive correlation of 0.418. However, there are no relationship for pre-test and post-test for female counterpart in the experimental group. While in the control group the male and female students have strong positive correlation for the pre-test and post-test of 0.586 and 0.612. This implies that the experimental group performed better than the control group. It can be deduced from the

study that the use of project-based teaching method has improved the technical skill of electrical installation and maintenance work students (Omeje, 2011).

Hypothesis 1 was therefore not rejected since there is no significant difference in the mean performance score in Technical Skill Performance Test in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work between male and female students taught with project-based teaching method and those taught with conventional teaching method ($p= 0.000<0.05$). The difference in performance is caused by the project-based teaching method. This is in agreement with the findings of Addey, Robertson and Venville (2002) and Udouo (2005) who reported that there was no significant difference between boys and girls in their cognitive. They also agree with some literature evidence questioning the validity of sex difference in scholastic performance, since it depends among other things on student's innate level of intelligence and interest on the subject.

The interaction between gender and teaching methods showed no significant difference ($P\leq 0.05$). Obi (2021) reported that there was a significant difference in the mean performance score of boys and girls in favour of the boys. This is in agreement with Eze, Ezenwafor and Obi (2015) findings on sex difference achievement, though in their case, females performed better than the male. There is no obvious reason for sex to account for differences in exercise of project-based teaching method on skill development since both sexes think and show no physical or psychological difference in their thinking process skills.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that project-based teaching method was highly effective as the students mean test performance in the general post-test scores were higher than those taught with conventional teaching method.

Implication of the study

Some educational implications are derived from the findings of this study. First, the study revealed the efficacy of project-based teaching method on students overall technical skill development in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work, suggesting that its use would not only improve students' skill development but would also improve their academic achievement.

The study also revealed that the use of project-based teaching method could eradicate or minimize gender related differences in students' technical skill development in electrical installation and maintenance work.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teachers of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work and other technical subjects taught in technical colleges should adopt project-based teaching method to improve teaching and learning.
2. Electrical installation and maintenance work teachers should pay attention to the issue of gender differences in the classroom, and also eliminate contents, teaching methods and materials that introduces gender differences in technical skill development.
3. The supervisory agencies for technical education in the country should emphasize the use of project-based teaching method in the technical curriculum.
4. Since the use of project-based teaching method has proved to enhance the quality of students' technical skill development in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work, government and other stakeholders in technical education should encourage teachers of the subject to use it by providing relevant resources in order to stimulate and sustain students' interest in the subject.

REFERENCES

Abdulrahman, B.(2012).Comparative effects of demonstration and guided discovery instructional method on students' achievement in electrical installation and maintenance work in technical colleges in Minna and Suleja. *Unpublished Master's Thesis* Department of Industrial and Technology Education, Federal University of Technology Minna.

- Addey, P., Robertson, A. & Venville, G. (2002). Effects of cognitive acceleration programmes on year 1 pupils. *British journal of Educational psychology* 12(1)1-25
- Agbejeye S. J. & Adegbola A. J. (2017). Gender and workshop facilities as determinant of student' performance in tertiary technical institution for sustainable economic recovery in Nigeria. *Journal of Nigerian Association of Teachers of Technology (JONATT)*, 211 – 218.
- Aguba, C.R. (2016). *Achieving national greatness through education that matters search higher on teacher education*. A lead paper presented at the 4th South East COEASU zonal conference held at Enugu State college of Education (Technical) Enugu, September, 8 – 17.
- Amaechi, O.J &Thoman, C.G (2016).Strategies of effective teaching and learning practical skills in technical and vocational training in Nigeria .*Information Journal of Scientific Research Engineering and Technology*, 5(2),598-603 Retrieved 26th September 2017 from www.ijret.org.
- Ayonmike, C. S. (2014) Comparative effectiveness of three teaching methods on students' psychomotor performance in brick/block-laying and concreting in Delta State College. *Unpublished Ph.D Thesis*. Department of Vocational Technology Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Bello, H. &Aliyu, U.O. (2012) Effect of Dick and Carey instructional model on the performance of electrical/electronic technology education students in some selected concepts in technical colleges of Northern Nigeria. Retrieved on 5th June 2018 from <http://www.intresjournals.org/ER>.
- Duze, C. (2011). Falling standard in Nigeria education. Traceable to proper skill acquisition in schools. *Edu. Res.* 2(1):808-820'
- Edu, D.O, Ayang, E.E, &Idaka, I (2012).Evaluation of instructional methods and aptitude effects on the psychomotor performance in basic electricity among technical students in southern educational zone, Cross River State Nigeria.*American International Journal of ComtemporaryReseach*, 2 (2),117-123 Retrieve on 4th September 2017 from www.aijcrnet.com
- Eze, T.I. &Oguyi, S.O. (2018). Effects of problem-based teaching on students' academic performance in electrical installation and maintenance work in technical colleges in Edo State. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 7(2) ,666-678. Retrieved on September 2018 from www.isdsnet.com/ijds.
- Eze, T.I, Ezenwafor, J.I, & Obi, M.N. (2015).Effect of age and gender on academic achievement of vocational and technical education (VTE) students of a Nigerian university J. Emerge. *Trends Educ.Res. Policy Stud.* 6 (1): 96-101
- Hassan, B &Babawuro S. (2013).State of facilities for electrical installation and maintenance work trade in technical colleges in Bauchi State. Nigeria. *International Journal of Vocationaland Technical Education.* 5 (5),82-91 Retrieved on 7th Febuary 2018 from <http://www.academicjournal.org/IJVTE>.
- National Board for Technical Education. (2010). *Electrical/electronic technology curriculum and course specification*, Kaduna.
- Obi, C.O.C. (2021). Relative effectiveness of demonstration and project-based teaching methods in developing students' psychomotor skill and interest in electrical installation and maintenance work. *Unpublished Ph.D dissertation* Department of Vocational and Technology education Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka.
- Okoye, K.R.E. (2016). *Education that matters; roadmap to achieving and sustaining national development*. A key note address presented at the 4th South East COEASU zonal conference held at Enugu state college of Education (Technical) Enugu, September, 1-7.
- Olokede, N.O. &Olunsanjo, M.O.(2009). *Introduction to principle and method of teaching* (2nd edition) Abuja: Akitol Prints.
- Ombugus, D.A. &Umaru, R.I. (2016). Psycho - productive skill multiple choice test items for assessing students in mechanical engineering craft in technical colleges. *Journal of Education Studies* Retrieved on 16th March 2017 from <http://www.Oapub.org/edu>

- Omeye, H.O. (2011) Effects of project-based learning instructional techniques on interest and retention of low ability students in woodwork. *Journal of Nigerian Association of Teachers of Technology (NATT)*, 7(3), 20-33.
- Omeje, H.O. & Onaga, P.O (2015). *Teaching vocational and technical education*. Quip techs Creation Enugu.
- Udoudo, N.J (2005). Effects of multiple-intelligence-based instructional approach on students' cognitive achievement and retention in introductory technology *unpublished M.Ed thesis* University of Nigeria Nsukka.
- Uzoagulu A. E. (2011) *Practical guide to writing research project Reports in tertiary institutions*. Cheston Ltd. Enugu, Nigeria.
- Yinusa, A.F. (2014). Assessment of teaching strategies adopted for effective implementation of science subject and trade modules curriculum in Nigeria technical colleges. *Journal of Educational and Social Research MCSER Publishing. Roman Italy*, 4(6), 391-396.